

WAYS OF SPIRITUAL FORMATION OF PRIMARY CLASS STUDENTS THROUGH TECHNOLOGY LESSONS

Shermatova Mahfuza

Teacher of Namangan State University

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Abstract: Spirituality is an incomparable force that calls a person to spiritual purification, spiritual growth, strengthens his inner world, strengthens his will, completes his faith, awakens his conscience, and is the criterion of all his views.

Keywords: meaningful, meaning, spirituality, national, tradition, maturity, inner strength, inner world faith, power, religious and worldly knowledge.

Spirituality is such a powerful concept that it can be considered as a concept that represents the spiritual and mental world of a person. It includes philosophical, legal, scientific, artistic, moral, religious ideas and inner world of people. The book "New Uzbekistan Strategy" by Shavkat Mirziyoyev was published on September 9, 2021. In the "Spiritual Development" section, the President explained about spirituality with special comments that it is a great foundation for the development of the people and society, and called on the youth to develop spiritually and mature spiritually.

The term spirituality is based on the word "meaning". There is an external and internal world of a person, and spiritual development takes place during life. The external world of a person includes his height, appearance, clothes, behavior, facial expressions. His inner world includes his purpose of living, inner world, inner feeling, thoughts, dreams, aspirations, feelings. This inner world of a person is the spiritual beauty, which defines a person's human virtue.

"If the body of society is economy, then its soul and spirit is spirituality. As we decide to build a new Uzbekistan, we rely on two strong pillars. The first is a strong economy based on market principles, and the second is a strong spirituality based on the rich heritage of our ancestors and national values" - President Shavkat Mirziyoyev said with these words that spirituality is a great force that glorifies and elevates a person and society. It was not for nothing that the President said that education should begin with national education, and spiritual education is the basis of national education. Our national curriculum is not called the national curriculum for nothing. Because, along with the development of the society, awareness of the identity, learning of national customs, preservation, love of the motherland and honoring the motherland are cultivated. The stability of society is determined by its spirituality. That's why one of the main tasks of education today is to educate young people to become spiritually mature in the spirit of national traditions and customs.

Elementary school students providing spiritual education through national education during each lesson through technology lessons is determined by contributing to the development of society. It is difficult to imagine spirituality without the roots of the nation formed over centuries, its historical experiences and socio-cultural development.

"Spirituality is the strength of a person, nation, society, and state. Where there is no happiness, there will never be happiness," said Islam, the first president of Uzbekistan Karimov . For this reason , the promotion of spirituality in Uzbekistan has been raised to the level of state policy. Thanks to the independence, the way was opened for young people to study the rich historical, scientific, cultural and religious heritage of the Uzbek people for many centuries, to use it as a common and priceless property of the people.

As a creative science, technology teaches us to understand our history, our identity, helps students to acquire a profession, and by studying the types of work, students are brought up in the spirit of national customs and traditions. This, of course, requires pedagogues to have a great deal of experience in the educational process, to approach work with responsibility, to constantly work on themselves.

Educating young people to become mentally mature is one of the urgent problems of today. Primary school technology lessons should be used to educate students to become mature, and to educate them in the national spirit. Primary school technology as a creative subject provides students with comprehensive, national customs, universal values, and national traditions. educates the mind to maturity in the soul. It requires great and serious attention. It is appropriate to give spiritual lessons to students through religious and secular knowledge in the family and in public places . The first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan said: "Read the book "High spirituality is an invincible power" to your children every day in the family, and continue from where you left off the next day." Educate spiritually, read books, educate through the heritage of our ancestors, don't educate sitting at the table surfing, educate purposefully, from hadiths that develop meaning, rules of etiquette, factors that call for education and upbringing, religious and secular those who expressed their opinion that you should educate them. In fact, food gives a person physical strength, spirituality gives him spiritual nourishment and strength. A person's morally mature education is closely related to the family environment, because in a healthy family, in a healthy environment, a child will definitely grow up smoothly, and in families with people of knowledge, children will definitely get an enviable upbringing. Not only in the family, in the society, but also on the streets, it is necessary to bring up young people meaningfully, because there is a saying that there are seven parents for a child.

Our spirituality has been formed, enriched and developed side by side with universal human values, starting from the teaching of "Avesta" and Zoroastrianism . Spirituality is related to enlightenment and culture. Since the science of technology is a creative science, it is very useful to educate students in a spiritual way, because in the science of technology, children learn about our nationality, history, architectural monuments, and traditions by studying each type of work. Spirituality does not appear ready-made in people. It can be achieved only through continuous study, study, research, and experience. In the course of practical work, students will learn about various professions and get acquainted with the hard work of our people.

The richer the spirituality, the more prosperous the society and the nation. They work tirelessly to improve people's living conditions, and work creates spiritual people. There is a saying in our nation that work glorifies a person. A spiritual person clearly knows what is the purpose of living, finds a way to spend his life meaningfully, acquires the culture of dealing , approaches every issue from the point of view of fairness and justice. Conscience, what is false and what is true, what is honor, what is halal and what is haraam - he can distinguish all these from each other, he will give up actions that lead to evil in life, and perform actions that lead to good. In the technology classes, the professions that glorify the hard work of a person - carpentry, sculpting, baking, carpentry, pottery and other professions - together with the explanation of the fact that the living conditions of a person behind these hard works should be better because of the hard work of the hardworking people. In the

science of technology, to introduce students to the hard work of the Uzbek people, to provide information about the creative works of the people, the paths taken by our great scientists on the way to the development of the nation, architectural monuments created by human hands, scientific always holding conversations about heritages, all good deeds, making political minutes, organizing lessons always in the national spirit, in the spirit of our traditions, customs, and spirituality. serves as a resource for thousands.

As the students develop spiritually through technology science in the elementary school, spiritual education continues in the circles as well. Educating students spiritually through science clubs and sports clubs determines the effective improvement of education. In the science of technology, students from "Skilled Hands", "Skilled Craftsmen", "Skilled Carpenter", "Master Plumber" and other circles get to know the secrets of all professions and trades. We can see that the good organization of the circles improves the morale of the students enough to find their place in life. In the organization of various pageants, contests, public works, exhibitions, only if there are sources that promote the factors that serve the comprehensive development of students, it will motivate young people to achieve excellence in all aspects, of course. elementary school technology as a creative subject is the basis for this.

students must apply the knowledge they have acquired in the field of technology in circles and develop projects that achieve results in practice, which is determined by contributing to the development of society.

High spirituality reflects the meaning of human life. Love of country, patriotism is one of the main factors determining human spirituality. Through the science of technology, we study our history, introducing people to the work of various professions to improve the living conditions of people, morally conveying that the beauty of life is the work of hardworking people creates a foundation for the meaningful development of society. In societies where spirituality has matured, the possessors of abilities and talents are the face, pride, and prestige of this society, the nation. In a spiritual society, reason, common sense, justice and good behavior are the priority. In such a society, people's faith in the future will be strong, various evils unbecoming of a person will disappear, society will develop.

In conclusion, it is the task of pedagogues to educate elementary school students from a young age to be mature, and it is required to organize work in cooperation with parents and the team at the level of responsibility. As a creative subject, technology classes have many opportunities to educate students to become spiritually mature, because through science, they learn about our nationality, traditions, history, and are educated in the spirit of patriotism. Spiritual education should serve to improve the material and spiritual world of the people in setting long-term goals that are carried out slowly, step by step, continuously .

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